

Prompt 01: Geração de Requisitos não funcionais

Given a user story, generate one or more relevant non-functional requirements, considering the intent of the functionality and possible failures or exceptions. Requirements should be clear, specific, written in a declarative manner, and classified by type (such as performance, security, usability, reliability, etc.). Take into account factors such as user experience, technical limitations, operational risks, and best practices from similar systems. Focus on requirements that ensure quality, robustness, and error prevention in the actual use of the described functionality.